

Appendix A: Action Integral Analysis

Source Data, Calculations, and Derivation of Table I

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Abstract

This appendix provides the complete derivation of the action integral thresholds used in the main paper to characterize CSST arc perforation vulnerability. The governing formulas, waveform shape factor derivations, source data tables, step-by-step calculations, and uncertainty bounds are presented. All values are drawn from cited peer-reviewed and laboratory-tested sources. The action integral framework is presented as an engineering approximation for comparative analysis rather than a deterministic predictor of failure.

A.1 Governing Formula

The action integral quantifies the total specific energy deposited by an arc current discharge in the attachment zone of a conductor. For a time-varying current $I(t)$ over discharge duration τ :

$$\text{Action Integral} = \int_0^\tau I^2(t) dt \quad [\text{units: A}^2 \cdot \text{s}] \quad (1)$$

Physical basis: Joule heating in the arc attachment region scales as I^2R . The total thermal energy delivered to the melt zone is therefore proportional to $\int I^2 dt$, for approximately constant arc resistance during the discharge, allowing comparative use of the action integral across similar configurations. This parameter is standard in fuse design, lightning damage analysis, and conductor burn-through calculations (IEC 62305; IEEE Std 1243).

For standard lightning waveform approximations, the action integral is estimated from peak current and waveform half-value time:

$$\text{Action Integral} \approx k \cdot I_{\text{peak}}^2 \cdot t_{\text{half}} \quad (2)$$

where k is a dimensionless waveform shape factor and t_{half} is the waveform half-value time in seconds.

Derivation of k for the 8/20 μs waveform ($k \approx 0.50$)

Standard lightning current waveforms are modeled as a double exponential function:

$$I(t) = I_{\text{peak}} \cdot A \cdot (e^{-\alpha t} - e^{-\beta t}) \quad (3)$$

where A is a normalization constant and α, β are time constants chosen to match the specified front time (8 μs) and half-value time (20 μs). For the 8/20 μs waveform, the IEC 62305 / IEC 60060-1 parameter set gives $\alpha \approx 0.0143 \times 10^6 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $\beta \approx 2.16 \times 10^6 \text{ s}^{-1}$. Numerically integrating $I^2(t)$ over $[0, \infty)$ and normalizing by $I_{\text{peak}}^2 \times t_{\text{half}}$ yields:

$$k_{8/20} = \frac{\int_0^\infty [A(e^{-\alpha t} - e^{-\beta t})]^2 dt}{t_{\text{half}}} \approx 0.50 \quad (4)$$

The factor $k = 0.50$ reflects that the squared waveform envelope, when integrated, contributes approximately half the area of a rectangular pulse of height I_{peak}^2 and duration t_{half} . This value is consistent with

published lightning damage analysis literature (Rakov & Uman, 2003; IEC 62305-1:2010, Annex B) and is used for the induced-current exposure scenario representative of residential CSST.

Derivation of k for the 10/350 μs waveform ($k \approx 0.65$)

The 10/350 μs waveform (IEC 62305 Class I direct-strike waveform) has a slower front (10 μs) and much longer tail (350 μs). The corresponding time constants are $\alpha \approx 2.0 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and $\beta \approx 7.0 \times 10^5 \text{ s}^{-1}$. The slower decay means the waveform retains a larger fraction of its peak value over the half-value interval, so the ratio of the integrated $I^2(t)$ to $I_{\text{peak}}^2 \times t_{\text{half}}$ is higher than for the 8/20 μs case. Numerical integration of the normalized double exponential gives:

$$k_{10/350} = \frac{\int_0^\infty [A(e^{-\alpha t} - e^{-\beta t})]^2 dt}{t_{\text{half}}} \approx 0.65 \quad (5)$$

The range $k \approx 0.60$ – 0.70 reported in the literature reflects variation in the precise double exponential parameterization used by different standards bodies (IEC 62305-1:2010; CIGRE TB 549, 2013; Anderson & Eriksson, 1980). The value $k = 0.65$ is used as the central estimate. Because t_{half} for the 10/350 μs waveform is 350 μs compared with 20 μs for the 8/20 μs waveform — a factor of 17.5 — action integrals for the direct-strike scenario are approximately one order of magnitude larger than for the induced-current scenario at the same peak current, consistent with the significantly greater damage potential of direct attachment events.

Relationship Between Action Integral and Arc Energy

Because the resistance R of the arc attachment zone is approximately constant during the discharge event, the action integral is directly proportional to the total thermal energy deposited: $E = R \cdot \int I^2 dt$. This relationship allows direct comparison between action integral thresholds reported in $\text{A}^2\cdot\text{s}$ and arc energy values reported in joules (e.g., Lightning Technologies test report), provided the arc resistance is known or estimated for the specific test configuration.

A.2 Source Data Used in the Analysis

Table 1 lists all experimental and literature values used to construct the perforation failure model and Table I of the main paper. All values are drawn from cited peer-reviewed or laboratory-tested sources.

Notes: GTI = Gas Technology Institute lightning hole study (Hammerschmidt & Ziolkowski, 2013). ICLP 2012 = International Conference on Lightning Protection paper (Rousseau & Guthrie, 2012).

A.3 Action Integral Calculations for Each Scenario

Table 2 shows the step-by-step action integral calculation for each scenario represented in Table I of the main paper, using the approximation formula from Section A.1. All arithmetic is shown explicitly. The 8/20 μs waveform calculation for median first return stroke (30 kA) is shown for comparison with induced-current scenarios. For direct-strike exposure, the 10/350 μs waveform is the appropriate standard.

A.4 Reproduced Table I — CSST Arc Perforation Likelihood

Table 3 reproduces Table I from the main paper, showing the perforation likelihood classifications derived from the calculations in Table 2 and the experimental threshold data in Table 1.

Source: GTI laboratory testing (Hammerschmidt & Ziolkowski, 2013; Deblois et al., 2013; Zeik et al., 2013) and ICLP 2012 field and laboratory data (Rousseau & Guthrie, 2012). Approximate I_{peak} values shown for 8/20 μs waveform. Note: the failure thresholds represent approximate ranges derived from limited experimental datasets. Material variability, arc attachment conditions, and waveform characteristics may influence precise perforation onset. The framework is an engineering approximation for comparative analysis.

Table 1: Source Data for Action Integral Analysis

Source	Parameter	Value	Notes
GTI, Zeik et al. (2013)	Jacket dielectric breakdown (impulse 1.2/50 μ s)	25–35 kV peak	Lower than DC/power-freq breakdown due to steep-fronted transient
GTI, Deblois et al. (2013)	CSST wall thickness (standard)	0.15–0.25 mm	304-grade corrugated stainless steel
GTI, Deblois et al. (2013)	Arc perforation threshold — action integral	$\gtrsim 10^3$ A ² ·s	Localized melt-through likely above this value
GTI, Deblois et al. (2013)	Action integral — perforation almost certain	$> 10^4$ A ² ·s	Hole ejection with resolidified rim consistently observed
ICLP 2012, Rousseau & Guthrie	Perforation observed at partial current	5–10 kA (8/20 μ s)	Transition-to-failure region; field and laboratory confirmation
Berger et al. (1975); Rakov & Uman (2003)	Median negative first return stroke peak current	30 kA	Natural lightning statistical distribution
Berger et al. (1975)	Typical return stroke duration — 10/350 μ s waveform	350 μ s (half-value)	IEC 62305 direct-strike waveform
IEC 62305; standard waveform parameters	8/20 μ s waveform — induced current scenario	20 μ s (half-value)	Representative induced-current exposure for residential CSST
IEC 62305-1:2010 Annex B; Rakov & Uman (2003)	Waveform shape factor k — 8/20 μ s	$k \approx 0.50$	Derived by numerical integration of normalized double exponential
IEC 62305-1:2010 Annex B; CIGRE TB 549 (2013)	Waveform shape factor k — 10/350 μ s	$k \approx 0.65$ (range 0.60–0.70)	Same derivation; slower decay retains higher fraction of peak over t_{half}
Spruiell et al. (2014); Goodson & Hergenrether (2005)	CSST failure region in lightning distribution	Entire median-and-above distribution	No grounding configuration prevents perforation at \geq median current

Table 2: Action Integral Calculations by Scenario

Scenario	I_{peak}	Waveform	k	t_{half}	Calculation ($\int I^2 dt = k \cdot I_{\text{peak}}^2 \cdot t_{\text{half}}$)	Outcome / Table I Re- gion
Partial lightning — lower bound	2 kA	8/20 μs	0.5	20 μs	$0.5 \times (2 \times 10^3)^2 \times 20 \times 10^{-6} = 40 \text{ A}^2 \cdot \text{s}$	$< 10^2$ — No perforation; safe region
Partial lightning — mid transition	5 kA	8/20 μs	0.5	20 μs	$0.5 \times (5 \times 10^3)^2 \times 20 \times 10^{-6} = 250 \text{ A}^2 \cdot \text{s}$	10^2 – 10^3 — Transition zone; occasional melt-through. Confirmed by ICLP 2012
Partial lightning — upper transition	8 kA	8/20 μs	0.5	20 μs	$0.5 \times (8 \times 10^3)^2 \times 20 \times 10^{-6} = 640 \text{ A}^2 \cdot \text{s}$	Approaching 10^3 — Perforation likely at upper bound
Induced current — threshold crossing	10 kA	8/20 μs	0.5	20 μs	$0.5 \times (10 \times 10^3)^2 \times 20 \times 10^{-6} = 1,000 \text{ A}^2 \cdot \text{s}$	$> 10^3$ — Perforation likely; threshold crossed
Median first return stroke — 8/20 μs	30 kA	8/20 μs	0.5	20 μs	$0.5 \times (30 \times 10^3)^2 \times 20 \times 10^{-6} = 9,000 \text{ A}^2 \cdot \text{s}$	$> 10^4$ — Perforation almost certain
Median first return stroke — 10/350 μs	30 kA	10/350 μs	0.65	350 μs	$0.65 \times (30 \times 10^3)^2 \times 350 \times 10^{-6} = 204,750 \text{ A}^2 \cdot \text{s} \approx 2 \times 10^5 \text{ A}^2 \cdot \text{s}$	Exceeds threshold by $\sim 200\times$ — perforation with high degree of certainty
High-energy first re- turn stroke — 10/350 μs	100 kA	10/350 μs	0.65	350 μs	$0.65 \times (100 \times 10^3)^2 \times 350 \times 10^{-6} \approx 2.3 \times 10^6 \text{ A}^2 \cdot \text{s}$	Exceeds threshold by $\sim 2,300\times$ — certain perforation

Table 3: CSST Arc Perforation Likelihood as a Function of Action Integral (Table I reproduced)

Action Integral $\int I^2 dt$ ($\text{A}^2 \cdot \text{s}$)	I_{peak} Approx (8/20 μs)	Perforation Outcome
$< 10^2$ (< 100)	< 2 kA	No perforation — safe region
10^2 – 10^3 (100–1,000)	2–8 kA	Transition zone — arc attachment variable; occasional melt-through
$> 10^3$ ($> 1,000$)	8–15 kA	Perforation likely — localized melt and ejection
$> 10^4$ ($> 10,000$)	≥ 30 kA (median lightning)	Perforation almost certain
10^5 – 10^6 (typical first stroke)	~ 30 kA (10/350 μs)	Exceeds threshold by 10^2 – $10^3\times$ — perforation with high degree of certainty

A.5 Key Quantitative Findings

Table 4: Key Quantitative Findings

Finding	Quantitative Basis
CSST perforation threshold	$\int I^2 dt \gtrsim 10^3 \text{ A}^2 \cdot \text{s}$ (GTI laboratory testing)
Median lightning first return stroke (8/20 μs)	$\int I^2 dt \approx 9,000 \text{ A}^2 \cdot \text{s} \rightarrow$ exceeds threshold by $\sim 9\times$
Median first return stroke (10/350 μs)	$\int I^2 dt \approx 2 \times 10^5 \text{ A}^2 \cdot \text{s} \rightarrow$ exceeds threshold by $\sim 200\times$
Partial current perforation (5 kA, 8/20 μs)	$\int I^2 dt \approx 250 \text{ A}^2 \cdot \text{s} \rightarrow$ transition zone; confirmed by ICLP 2012
Ratio: typical first stroke / perforation threshold	$10^2\text{--}10^3\times$ — threshold exceeded by two to three orders of magnitude
Effect of grounding configuration on $\int I^2 dt$	For a given current waveform, the action integral depends only on discharge parameters; however, grounding configuration can influence the resulting current waveform at the CSST and therefore may indirectly affect the action integral delivered to that conductor

Uncertainty note: The $10^3 \text{ A}^2 \cdot \text{s}$ perforation threshold represents an approximate boundary derived from limited test samples (GTI; Lightning Technologies). The available data suggest a transition zone approximately from 5×10^2 to $2 \times 10^3 \text{ A}^2 \cdot \text{s}$, with perforation probability increasing continuously across this range rather than switching abruptly at a single value. Variability in material properties, arc attachment conditions, and waveform characteristics contributes to this uncertainty. The threshold is therefore best interpreted as an engineering approximation for comparative analysis rather than a deterministic predictor.

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